

Rare tricyclic sesquiterpene lactones and related compounds from *Moscharia* and *Trixis* species[†]

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Abstract : The chemistry of eight isocedrenolides and an α -isocedrenial from the aerial parts of *Moscharia pinnatifida*, trixiparadoxin, its isovalerate and 2-methyl butyrate from the aerial parts of *Trixis inula*, five trixikingolides alongwith trixiparadoxin esters from the roots and the aerial parts of *Trixis paradoxa*, four trixikingolides from the aerial parts, 14 β -methoxytrixic acid methyl ester and trixiparadoxin isovalerate from the roots of *Trixis vautheri* and further five trixikingolides in addition to trixiparadoxin isovalerate from the roots and the aerial parts of *Trixis antimenorrhoea* have been reviewed.

Keywords : Isocedrenolides, trixikingolides, *Moscharia pinnatifida*, *Trixis inula*, *T. paradoxa*, *T. vautheri*, *T. antimenorrhoea*, Asteraceae.

Introduction

The isocedrenolides and trixikingolides represent a rare class of tricyclic sesquiterpene lactones derived from α -isocedrene, I. α -Isocedrene has two fused five membered and one six membered rings with one double bond. It also contains an olefinic, a secondary and a gem dimethyl group at C-5, C-7 and C-11, respectively in the molecule.

Isocedrenolides are formed by intramolecular cyclization of 14-hydroxy and 15-carboxylic groups while trixikingolides are derived by intramolecular cyclization of 4-hydroxy and 12-carboxylic functions. The suffix 'olide' in their name refers to the lactone moiety (internal ester) in the molecule.

Like other sesquiterpene lactones, these tricyclic sesquiterpene lactones also occur as acetate or carry other ester side chains. Acids frequently involved in esterifications are 4 or 5 carbon atoms and their names alongwith abbreviations are mentioned as methacrylic (Meacr), isobutyric (*i*-Bu), tiglic (Tigl), angelic (Ang), 2-methylbutyric (2-Mebu), senecioic (Sen), isovaleric (*i*-Val) acids and/or their hydroxy and acetoxy derivatives. The ester groups generally show diagnostic peaks in mass spectra. Commonly, the M-RCOOH and/or M-[CH₂=C=O] are detected as reasonably strong peaks and the peak due to acylium ion, RCO⁺, frequently represents the base peak.

The lactonic peaks in IR spectra appear around 1740 cm⁻¹ in addition to the peaks for other functional groups. These esters exhibit highly characteristic signals in their ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra.

The genus *Moscharia* and *Trixis* are placed in the family Asteraceae (Compositae), the tribe Mutisieae and subtribe Nassauviinae¹. Previously the roots of *Moscharia*

[†]In honour of Professor Sunit Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

pinnatifida Ruiz. et Pav. have been examined chemically affording only the widespread tridecapentayne². The aerial parts of *Trixis inula* were earlier investigated for a pair of trixiparadoxin esters³⁻⁵. Germacrene D was previously isolated from the aerial parts of *Trixis paradoxa* Cass³. The roots of *Trixis vautheri* DC. were earlier investigated for caryophyllene, the corresponding 1,10-epoxide and a pair of alantolactones^{6,7} while the roots and the aerial parts of *Trixis antimenorrhoea* (Schrank) Mart. have not been investigated so far.

In this brief review, the results of structure elucidation of isocedrenolides **1-8**, 7,8-dehydro- α -isocedrene-8,9-dial **9** from the aerial parts of *Moscharia pinnatifida*^{8,9}, trixiparadoxin **10**, its isovaleryloxy and 2-methylbutyryloxy derivatives **12, 13** from the aerial parts of *Trixis anula*¹⁰, trixikingolides **22, 23**, trixiparadoxin isovalerate and 2-methylbutyrate **12, 13** from the roots, **12, 13** and trixikingolides **14-16** from the aerial parts of *Trixis paradoxa*⁵, 14 β -methoxytrixic acid **11, 12**, trixikingolide **22** from the roots and **11**, trixikingolides **17-19, 22** from the aerial parts of *Trixis vautheri*⁴ and **12**, trixikingolide **22** from the roots and trixikingolides **22** and **20** from the aerial parts of *Trixis antimenorrhoea*⁴ have been discussed.

Results and discussion

The molecular formula C₁₉H₂₄O₆ for **4** was derived from high resolution mass spectrometry. The presence of two acetoxy groups in the molecule was established from the loss of two molecules of acetic acid in mass spectrum and the presence of two singlets at δ 2.06 and 2.07 integrated for three protons each in the ¹H NMR spectrum (Table 1). In deuteriobenzene all NMR signals were assigned by spin decoupling. Proton H-1 showed a W-coupling with H-10. The complete sequence could be established starting with the pair of doublets at δ 3.65 and 3.92 (H-14). H-12 and H-13 signals could only be assigned as shown in Table 1. All data were very similar to those of 14-hydroxy- α -isocedren-15-oic acid-14,15-lactone¹¹. The presence of two acetoxy groups, however, caused the expected changes in the spectrum of **4**. The stereostructure for **4** was deduced by NOE difference spectroscopy. Clear NOEs were observed between H-13 and H-1 β , H-2, H-12 and H-9 α , between H-9 α and H-7, between H-1 α and H-3 α , between H-10 and H-8, H-12 and H-12' and between H-8 β and H-14 β . These results agreed with the earlier proposed stereochemistry for this

Table 1. ¹H NMR spectral data (δ, ppm) of compounds **1-9** (400 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS as internal standard)

H	1	2	3	4	4 (C₆D₆)	5	6	7	8	9 (C₆D₆)
1α-H	1.90, br d	*	*	1.90, br d	1.31, br d	1.90, br d	1.90, br d	1.90, br d	1.90, br, d	2.08, dd
1β-H	2.08, dd	*	*	*	1.58, dd	*	*	*	*	1.51, dd
2-H	*	*	*	*	1.65, t	*	*	*	*	1.58, dd
3α-H	2.46, ddd	2.54, ddd	2.53, ddd	2.50, ddd	1.93, ddd	2.50, ddd	2.50, ddd	2.50, ddd	2.50, ddd	2.00, m
3β-H	2.54, ddd	2.45, ddd	2.45, ddd	2.43, ddd	2.03, ddd	2.43, ddd	2.43, ddd	2.43, ddd	2.43, ddd	2.00, m
4-H	6.80, br t	6.80, br t	6.80, br t	6.84, br t	6.77, br t	6.84, br t	6.84, br t	6.84, br t	6.84, br t	5.76, dt
7-H	*	2.28, dd	2.28, dd	*	1.60, ddd	*	*	*	*	-
8-H	4.23, ddd	5.02, ddd	5.02, ddd	5.06, ddd	5.08, ddd	5.08, ddd	5.08, ddd	5.11, ddd	5.06, ddd	5.95, br t
9α-H	*	1.52, ddd	1.52, ddd	1.54, m	1.24, ddd	1.54, m	1.54, m	1.54, m	1.54, m	2.04, ddd
9β-H	*	2.12, ddd	2.12, ddd	*	1.79, ddd	*	*	*	*	2.08, br dd
10-H	*	*	*	*	1.50, ddd	*	*	*	*	2.30, ddd
12-H	1.10, s	1.08, s	1.08, s	3.97, d	3.79, d	3.97, d	3.97, d	3.97, d	3.97, d	0.79, s
12-H	1.10, s	1.08, s	1.08, s	3.90, d	3.66, d	3.90, d	3.90, d	3.90, d	3.90, d	0.79, s
13-H	1.06, s	1.02, s	1.02, s	1.05, s	0.76, s	1.05, s	1.05, s	1.05, s	1.05, s	0.74, s
14α-H	4.24, d	5.62, m	5.62, m	4.21, m	3.65, dd	4.21, m	4.21, m	4.21, m	4.21, m	9.78, s
14β-H	4.40, d	5.62, m	5.62, m	-	3.92, dd					
15-H	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.23, s
OAc	-	-	-	2.06, s	1.72, s	2.06, s	2.06, s	2.06, s	2.06, s	-
				2.07, s	1.73, s	-	-	-	-	-

*Overlapped multiplets : OSen (**2** and **6**) : 5.65, qq; 2.18, d; 1.90, d; OiVal (**3** and **8**) : 2.19, d, 2.10, m, 0.94, d; OiBu (**5**) : 2.36, qq, 1.17, d; OAng (**7**) : 6.11, qq; 1.99, dq; 1.89, dq; *J* (Hz) : 1α,1β=12; 1α,2=1α,10=1; 1β,2=2,3α=4; 2,3β~1; 3α,3β=21; 3α,4=3; 3β,4=4; 7,8=6; 7,14α=4; 7,14β=3; 8,9α=13; 8,9β=7.5; 9α,9β=12.5; 9α,10=10; 9β,10=7.5; 12,12'=11.5; 14α,14β=12 (compound **1** : 7,14α=3; 7,14β=1.5; compounds **2** and **3** : 7,14=2; compound **9** : 4,15=0.5; 8,9α=8,9β=2.7; 9α,10=9β,10=9).

type of sesquiterpene lactone¹¹. The ¹³C NMR spectrum was in good agreement with the structure. The compound **4** was named as 8α,12-diacetoxy-14-hydroxy-α-isocedren-15-oic acid-14,15-lactone.

The ¹H NMR spectrum of **1** (Table 1) was more or less similar to that of **4**. However, the methylacetoxy signal was replaced by a methyl singlet and the H-8 signal shifted upfield. The values of coupling constants indicated identical stereochemistry as all chiral centres and accordingly it was characterized as 8α,14-dihydroxy-α-isocedren-15-oic acid-14,15-lactone. The ¹H NMR spectra of **5-8** exhibited that each of these lactones differed from **4** in the nature of one ester group. As the H-12 signals were not altered, 12-acetoxy derivatives were assumed in all the cases. Second ester residues in **5-8** were assigned as isobutyryloxy, seneciolyoxy, angeloyloxy and isovaleryloxy, respectively and were identified as 12-acetoxy-8α-isobutyryloxy-14-hydroxy-α-isocedren-15-oic acid-14,15-lactone **5**, 12-acetoxy-8α-seneciolyoxy-14-hydroxy-α-isocedren-15-oic acid-14,15-lactone **6**, 12-acetoxy-

8α-angeloyloxy-14-hydroxy-α-isocedren-15-oic acid-14,15-lactone **7** and 12-acetoxy-8α-isovaleryloxy-14-hydroxy-α-isocedren-15-oic acid-14,15-lactone **8**.

The spectra of **2** and **3** (Table 1) indicated that there were no oxygen function at C-12 while broadened low field signals as δ 5.62 showed a small coupling with H-7 and were due to H-14. Inspection of a model and the downfield shift of the H-7 signal exhibited that a 14α-hydroxy group was present while the three-fold doublets as δ 5.02 and 5.04 in **2** and **3** indicated that these lactones were also 8α-acyloxy derivatives and were characterized as 8α-seneciolyoxy-14-hydroxy-α-isocedren-15-oic acid-14,15-lactone **2** and 8α-isovaleryloxy-14-hydroxy-α-isocedren-15-oic acid-14,15-lactone **3**.

The molecular formula of **9** was C₁₅H₁₈O₂ and its ¹H NMR spectrum (Table 1) in deuteriobenzene revealed the presence of two aldehyde functions. The lowfield triplets at δ 5.76 and 5.95 could only be assigned to olefinic protons in β-positions to carbonyl groups. The remaining signals were close to those of the corresponding dialdehyde

from *Jungia malvaefolia*¹² which represents the corresponding 7,8-dihydro derivative of **9**. Accordingly, in the ¹H NMR spectrum of the α -isocedren-14,15-dial the second low field triplet (δ 5.95) was missing. As in similar cases, the *E*-configuration of the conjugated aldehydes followed from the chemical shifts of the aldehyde protons. The NMR signals of **9** displayed nearly the same couplings as those of **4-8**. However, several signals were shifted downfield due to second carbonyl group and the additional double bond and **9** was named as 7,8-dehydro- α -isocedren-14,15-dial.

The molecular formula of **10**, C₁₅H₁₈O₄ was determined by high resolution mass spectrometry. The ¹H NMR spectral data of **10** were of course close to those of the

isovalerate **12**⁴. The typical signals of H-3, H-4 and H-15 clearly indicated that again an isocedrene derivative was present while the IR spectrum showed that an acid had to be proposed. Spin decoupling allowed the assignment of most signals though those of H-8 and H-9 were overlapping multiplets. As the couplings and chemical shifts were nearly the same as in **12** identical stereochemistry in all derivatives was very likely. Accordingly, **10** was trixiparadoxin, the precursor of **12** and **13**.

The structure of the methyl ether **11** followed from the ¹H NMR data (Table 2), which clearly indicated that the stereochemistry as C-14 was changed if compared with that of **10**. As C-14 epimeric compounds have already been prepared³, the assignment of the configura-

Table 2. ¹H NMR spectral data (δ , ppm) of compounds **10-16** (270 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS as internal standard)

H	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
1 α -H	1.98, m	2.00, m	1.85, m	1.85, m	1.42, dd	1.45, dd	1.37, dd
1 β -H			2.09, m	2.09, m	3.05, ddd	3.18, dd	3.07, ddd
2-H	2.61, br dd	2.60, br dd	2.64, br dd	2.64, br dd	2.38, br dd	2.40, m	2.38, br dd
3 α -H	5.85, dd	5.75, dd	5.81, m	5.81, m	1.90, m	4.97, dd	1.87, m
3 β -H					2.13, dddd	-	2.13, dddd
4-H	5.88, d	5.83, d	5.81, m	5.81, m	4.87, ddd	4.88, dd	4.83, ddd
7-H	1.98, m	2.0, m	2.06, dd	2.06, dd	2.53, ddd	2.60, ddd	2.54, ddd
8 α -H	1.5-1.9, m	1.4-1.9, m	1.8, m	1.8, m	1.9, m	1.9, m	1.9, m
8 β -H							
9 α -H	1.5-1.9, m	1.4-1.9, m	1.44, m	1.44, m	-	-	-
9 β -H					4.48, ddd	4.42, dd	4.41, ddd
10-H	2.85, dd	2.85, dd	2.87, dd	2.87, dd	2.20, m	2.20, m	2.20, m
13-H	1.35, s	1.28, s	1.29, s	1.29, s	1.60, s	4.74, d	1.59, s
						4.61, d	
14-H	4.93, d	4.58, d	6.01, d	6.01, d	5.42, d	5.46, d	5.42, d
15-H	6.14, s	6.10, s	6.09, s	6.09, s	6.47, s	6.53, s	6.43, s
OAc	-	-	-	-	2.00, s	2.02, s	2.01, s
OMe		3.67, s	-	-	-	-	-
4'-OCOR			2.22, br d	2.39, tq	3.00, d	2.97, d	3.01, d
			2.1, m	1.67, m	2.95, d	2.86, d	2.94, d
			0.97, d	1.44, m	1.56, s	1.55, s	1.55, s
				0.91, t	1.59, s		1.54, s
				1.15, d			
OCOR					2.53, tq	2.29, br d	
					1.67, m	2.20, m	
					1.45, m	1.01, d	
					0.93, t	1.00, d	
					1.16, d		

J (Hz) : **10** and **11** : 1,2=4; 2,3=6; 3,4 = 9; 7,14 = 5.5; 9,10=8; **12** and **13** : 1 β ,2=3.5; 2,3=5.5; 3,4=9; 7,14= 3; 7,8 α =6; 9 α ,9 β =13; 9 α ,10=7; 9 β ,10=9 ; **14-16** : 1 α ,1 β =11; 1 α ,2=1.5; 1 β ,2= 6; 1 β ,3 β =1.5; 2,3 α =6; 2,3 β =2; 2,4 α =1.5; 7,8 α =6; 7,14=9; 8 α ,8 β =14; 8 β ,9 β =4; 9 β ,OH=4; 9 β ,10 =4; compound **14** : 13,13'=10.5; compound **10** : 2,3 α =3 α ,4=2.5.

tion was easy. A singlet at δ 3.67 indicated the presence of OMe group in the compound along with a doublet at δ 4.58 for the proton under oxygen function. It was named as 14 β -methoxytrixic acid⁴. The structure of the esters **12** and **13** were very close to that of **10**, these differing only in the nature of ester residues at position C-14. Consequently, H-14 proton appeared as a downfield doublet at δ 6.01 and these were characterized as trixiparadoxin isovalerate **12** and the corresponding 2-methyl butyrate **13**.

The structures of **14-16** were deduced from their ¹H NMR spectral data (Table 2). The presence of 4,12-lactone was ascertained by the conspicuous absence of H-12 signal and shifting of 4 β -H proton to downfield (δ 4.87). Acetoxy isovaleryloxy residue was assigned in all these lactones at C-14 by the further downfield shift of H-14 proton. Additional 2-methylbutyryloxy group in **14** was fixed as C-13 by the appearance of a pair of doublets at δ 4.74 and 4.61 in place of H-13 singlet. The presence of isovaleryloxy function in **15** at C-3 was assigned by the appearance of H-3 signal as a double doublet at δ 4.97 while **16** did not have additional signals for any ester group. Subsequently these lactones were named as 9 α -hydroxy-13-[2-methylbutyryloxy]-trixikingolide-[3'-acetoxy isovalerate] 9 α -hydroxy-3 β -isovaleryloxy-trixikingolide[3'-acetoxy isovalerate] and 9 α -hydroxy-trixikingolide-[3'-acetoxy isovalerate], respectively.

The structures of **17-19** were derived from the ¹H NMR spectral data (Table 3). However, the data were all very close to those of the 9 α -hydroxy trixikingolide diesters⁵. From the ¹H NMR data the nature of the ester groups were clearly established, but the relative positions of the different esters caused difficulties. In case of **17**, partial saponification was successful and this allowed structural assignment since in the ¹H NMR spectrum of the resulting diol **21**, the H-14 signal was shifted upfield and the signals of the acetoxy isovalerate were still present. As **18** was an isomer of **17**, its structure was also clear.

If the signals of the hydroxymethylbutyrate residues in the spectra of **17** and **18** are compared, slight difference in the chemical shifts can be observed, which surely were caused by the lactone carbonyl. The relative positions of the ester residues in **19** could not be deduced with certainty. As partial saponification was not possible, the presence of hydroxy acid at C-14 was less likely, as

Table 3. ¹H NMR spectral data (δ , ppm) of compounds **17-21** (270 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS as internal standard)

H	17	18 +D ₂ O	19	20	21
1 α -H	1.44, dd	1.44, dd	1.45, dd	1.43, dd	1.40, m
1 β -H	3.16, dd	3.17, dd	3.16, dd	3.15, dd	3.17, dd
2-H	2.38, ddd	2.38, ddd	2.38, ddd	2.39, ddd	2.38, br d
3 α -H	4.95, dd	4.95, dd	4.95, dd	4.96, dd	4.94, dd
3 β -H	-	-	-	-	-
4-H	4.87, dd	4.87, dd	4.86, dd	4.83, dd	4.87, dd
7-H	2.62, ddd	2.62, ddd	2.60, ddd	2.62, ddd	2.4, m
8 α -H	2.23, dd	2.23, dd	2.22, dd	2.23, dd	2.2, m
8 β -H	1.87, ddd	1.88, ddd	1.87, ddd	1.89, ddd	1.6, m
9 α -H	-	-	-	-	-
9 β -H	4.42, dd	4.41, dd	4.41, dd	4.40, dd	4.41, dd
10-H	2.18, br d	2.17, br d	2.18, br d	2.18, br d	2.1, m
13-H	1.59, s	1.59, s	1.59, s	1.60, s	1.53, s
14-H	5.47, d	5.48, d	5.49, d	5.44, d	4.50, d
15-H	6.53, s	6.53, s	6.52, s	6.49, s	6.51, s

OCOCH₂C(OAc)Me₂ : 2.95, d and 2.85, d (*J* 14.5 Hz); 1.52, s, 2.00, s; OCOCH(Me)CH(OH)Me : 2.56, dq and 3.9, dq (*J* 7, 7, Hz); 1.25, d and 1.21, d (*J* 7 Hz) [in **18** : 2.59, dq and 4.11, dq (*J* 7, 4.5 Hz), 1.24, d, 1.23, d (*J* 7 Hz)]; OCOCH₂C(OH)Me₂ : 2.58, s, 1.33, s, 1.31, s; COCH(Me)Et : 2.34, ddq (*J* 7, 7, 7 Hz), 1.64, ddq and 1.43, ddq (*J* 14, 7, 7 Hz), 1.13, d and 0.89, d (*J* 7 Hz); OCOCH (Me)CH(OAc)Me : 2.80, dq (*J* 7, 7 Hz), 5.16, dq (*J* 7, 7 Hz), 1.25, d and 1.20, d (*J* 7 Hz). *J* (Hz) : **17** : 1 α ,1 β =12; 1 α ,2=1.5; 1 β ,2=6; 2,3 α =3 α ,4=2.5; 7,8 α =8.5; 7,8 β =6.5; 7,14=9; 8 α ,8 β =15; 8 β ,9 β =9 β ,10=5.

obviously the success in case of **17** was highly influenced by the lability of such an acid function. These were characterized as 9 α -hydroxy-3 β -[3'-acetoxyisovaleryloxy]-trixikingolide-3'-hydroxy-2'-methylbutyrate **17**, 9 α -hydroxy-3 β -[3'-hydroxy-2'-methylbutyryloxy]-trixikingolide-3'-acetoxy isovalerate **18** and 9 α -hydroxy-3 β -[3'-hydroxy isovaleryloxy]-trixikingolide-3'-acetoxy isovalerate **19**.

The molecular formula of **20** was C₂₇H₃₆O₁₀. The ¹H NMR spectral data (Table 3) showed the presence of a 2-methylbutyrate and a β -acetoxy-2-methylbutyrate groups while the other signals were more or less the same as those of **17** to **19**. A small upfield shift of the H-14 signal led to the proposed structure **20** as the more likely one. The absence of a β -oxygen function at the ester residue was obviously the reason for this difference in chemical shifts. Again, partial saponification was unsuccessful. It was named as 9 α -hydroxy-3 β -[3'-acetoxy-2'-methylbutyryloxy]-trixikingolide-2'-methylbutyrate.

The chemistry of the genera *Moscharia* and *Trixis* agrees well with the placement of these genera in the subtribe Nassauviinae, the members of which have already yielded some α -isocedrene derivatives^{11,12,3-5}. This type of sesquiterpene has not been reported from any other group. Nothing is known about the chemistry of the other genera placed in the subtribe Nassauviinae. Most of them are small genera.

The subtribe Nassauviinae is the most natural in the tribe Mutisieae and is also morphologically quite uniform¹. From a taxonomic viewpoint some unspecialized *Trixis* are proposed to be the basic group in the subtribe. The presence of isocedrenolides **1-8** in the genus *Moscharia*^{3,4} may be an indication that these compounds are specialized sesquiterpenes. Their biogenesis developed very early and may be restricted to the group. The proposed grouping of the subtribe¹³ does not agree very well with the chemistry. However, investigations of more species from the whole tribe will be necessary to get a clear picture both from the chemical and from the taxonomic points of view.

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References

1. A. L. Cabrera, "The Biology and Chemistry of the Compositae", eds. V. H. Heywood, J. B. Harborne and B. L. Turner, Academic Press, London, 1977, pp. 1036-1066.
2. F. Bohlmann, T. Burkhardt and C. Zdero, "Naturally Occurring Acetylenes", Academic Press, London, 1973, p. 462.
3. F. Bohlmann and C. Zdero, *Chem. Ber.*, 1979, **112**, 435.
4. F. Bohlmann, A. Suwita, J. Jakupovic, R. M. King and H. Robinson, *Phytochemistry*, 1981, **20**, 1649.
5. F. Bohlmann, C. Zdero, R. M. King and H. Robinson, *Phytochemistry*, 1979, **18**, 855.
6. F. Bohlmann, C. Zdero, H. Robinson and R. M. King, *Phytochemistry*, 1981, **20**, 1631.
7. F. Bohlmann, C. Zdero, R. M. King and H. Robinson, *Phytochemistry*, 1980, **19**, 689.
8. Pahup Singh, J. Jakupovic and F. Bohlmann, *Phytochemistry*, 1985, **24**, 1525.
9. Pahup Singh and Archana Suri, *Phytochemistry*, 1990, **29**, 3944.
10. X. A. Dominguez, Pahup Singh and F. Bohlmann, *Rev. Latinoamer. Quim.*, 1985, **16-1**, 46.
11. F. Bohlmann, C. Zdero, R. M. King and H. Robinson, *Phytochemistry*, 1983, **22**, 1201.
12. F. Bohlmann and C. Zdero, *Chem. Ber.*, 1979, **112**, 427.
13. J. V. Crisci, *J. Arnold. Abor.*, 1974, **55**, 38.